

Evaluating adaptive directionality using the Spatial Speech in Noise Test

Bhavisha Parmar ^{a,b*}, Gordon Mills ^a, Deborah Vickers ^b, Jennifer K. Bizley ^a

^a UCL Ear Institute, University College London, 332 Grays Inn Road, London, WC1X 8EE,

^b Sound Lab, Cambridge Hearing Group, University of Cambridge, Biomedical Campus, Cambridge. CB2 0SZ

* Contact author: bp472@cam.ac.uk

Abstract

A Spatial Speech in Noise test (SSiN) was developed by Bizley et al (2015) and offers the potential to assess both spatial discrimination and the ability to use spatial information for unmasking in clinical populations. The dual nature of the SSiN task has the potential to increase cognitive load, therefore reflecting more challenging listening scenarios. This double-blind study aims to determine whether the SSiN can be used to assess adaptive directionality in hearing aids. Six adult, experienced hearing aid users completed the SSiN with and without adaptive directionality activated. A focus group was carried out involving the SSiN participants to evaluate the usability of the SSiN. Adaptive directionality resulted in reduced reaction times to SSiN stimuli compared to the omnidirectional (OMNI) setting. There was no significant difference in word identification between conditions. Relative localisation was significantly worse in the adaptive directionality condition. During qualitative review, participants reported improvement indicators to enhance usability. SSiN findings include measures of spatial acuity based on word identification, spatial release from masking, relative localisation and reaction time (as a proxy for listening effort). The use of speech stimuli and multisource babble allows for an engaging task that replicates the challenges of real-world listening. Here, the SSiN has been used to assess adaptive directionality and findings are consistent with previous literature that suggests adaptive directionality reduces listening effort, even when there is no noticeable enhancement of speech perception. We have also presented some indicators to improve future applications of the SSiN.

Introduction

A hearing aid users' individual aided speech intelligibility in dynamic situations can be impacted by a multitude of factors including both device factors (noise reduction, directional microphones, remote microphones) and patient factors (age, attention, tiredness, cognition). Traditionally, hearing aid processing algorithms were designed to improve speech intelligibility in a variety of ways including enhancing the spectro-temporal contrast in order to help the listener gain more from the spectro-temporal structure of the sound source (Baer et al., 1993). However, the most common ways to enhance the target speech source and suppress the competing noise, are to use noise suppression algorithms and directional microphones to optimise the intelligibility of the target speech (Ricketts & Dittberner, 2002).

Digital noise reduction has been available in hearing aids since the mid-1990s and hearing aid manufacturers have created and evaluated various advanced noise reduction algorithms over the years. However, there is limited evidence suggesting these systems successfully improve speech intelligibility (Lakshmi et al., 2021). Overall, research has indicated that directional microphones offer listeners an advantage when compared to amplification alone (Boymans & Dreschler, 2000; Cord et al., 2002; Yueh et al., 2001). However, listeners often do not report any self-rated

preference of directional microphone compared to omni-directional microphones (Cord et al., 2002; Palmer et al., 2006).

A variety of assessment methods have been used in hearing aid research to measure the benefit of noise reduction and directionality features. Within the clinical domain, there are no specific guidelines on the use or validation of noise reduction or directional microphones for patients with hearing aids. Additionally, speech perception testing in quiet and in noise, is performed infrequently in some countries (Parmar et al 2021), with the lack of clinical time being a key barrier to uptake. Therefore, a spatial speech in noise task (Bizley et al., 2015) has been developed to be an efficient, ecologically valid, method of simultaneously assessing relative localisation and word identification performance, using a dual response paradigm. In addition, reaction time data is recorded to provide information on a listener's listening effort. Such a dynamically changing task could be used to better understand the benefit of advanced hearing aid features, including adaptive directionality and noise reduction features in complex listening environments.

The present study investigates the feasibility of using the SSiN to assess advanced hearing aid features. A double-blind behavioural design was used alongside technical hearing aid output measurements and a follow up focus group was conducted to explore the SSiN user experience.

Method

Ethical considerations

This study received ethical approval from University College London (UCL) Research Ethics Committee (3865/001). No participant identifiable data is presented in this paper. Data was kept in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679. All listeners signed an informed consent document and were reimbursed for their efforts.

Participants

Adult experienced bilateral hearing aid users ($n = 6$) with moderate sensorineural hearing loss in both ears. Participants were native English-speaking adults over the 40 years of age with adult-onset hearing loss. Hearing loss criteria was bilateral symmetrical moderate (to severe) sensorineural hearing loss bilaterally. Participants were experienced hearing aid users with over 2 years of hearing aid use with no known cognitive or neurological disorders.

Figure 1 — Audiometric thresholds for all participants. The bold black line indicates group mean thresholds.

Study Design

A prospective, doubled blind trial to assess the value of the SSiN to assess Oticon's Open Sound Navigator™. Hearing aid technical measurements were carried out to investigate output signal to noise ratio in response to the SSiN testing paradigm and a focus group was held to explore the user experience.

Hearing aid fitting

Audiological assessment included otoscopic examination and pure tone audiometry. Participants had Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) scores ≥ 26 as this is the cited cut off for mild cognitive impairment (Nasreddine et al., 2005). Participants were fitted bilaterally with Oticon Opn™ receiver-in-the-canal hearing aids coupled with occluded domes and given an acclimatisation period of 4-6 weeks.

The hearing aids were fitted with the default OMNI microphone mode for everyday listening. The initial programmed settings were duplicated on the hearing aid software to ensure the second programme had identical gain characteristics as the first. One programme was set to OMNI, and one was set to adaptive directionality setting, Open Sound Navigator™ (OSN). Programmes could be selected by using a paired smartphone app or the programme switch on the back of the hearing aid. In the OMNI setting, noise reduction was deactivated and "pinna omni" was selected in the hearing aid software. In the OSN setting, noise reduction and automatic directionality were activated. OSN was set to the strongest setting within the Oticon Genie Software by setting "Noise Reduction Simple" to -3 dB, "Open Sound Transition" to high and "Noise Reduction Complex" to -9 dB. Both programmes were otherwise identical and feedback suppression and volume controls were deactivated. The configuration of these two programmes matched that of Browning et al. (2019), and it was hypothesised that they would give the largest noticeable difference in output signal to noise ratio (dB SNR) within the SSiN testing paradigm. To ensure double blind testing, a technician otherwise uninvolved in this work assigned each test condition (either OSN or OMNI) randomly to a number and this information was only released to the author upon completion of data collection.

Open sound navigator

Oticon's Open Sound Navigator (OSN) is an adaptive directionality and speech enhancement algorithm that was released by Oticon in 2016 to preserve speech and reduce noise from complex environments (Le Goff et al., 2016). One of its objectives is to apply directionality and noise reduction after the analysis of the competing sounds. The system was created to preserve speech and attempts to detect any speech like modulations in 16 frequency bands. If speech is detected in a frequency band, the algorithm is deactivated in that band. Therefore, OSN should preserve speech regardless of the listener's position in the environment. OSN combines fully adaptive directionality and fast-acting noise reduction.

Spatial Speech in Noise Test (SSiN)

An adapted version of the Spatial Speech in noise test (SSiN) developed by Bizley et al (2015) was used in the present study. Monosyllabic words (Table I) and multi talker babble were presented from speakers highlighted in Figure 2. The testing parameters were identical to the original study apart from a number of amendments that were made to enhance ecological validity and method of testing hearing aid features. These amendments were also implemented to avoid floor effects observed in our pilot experiments (Parmar et al., 2018):

- Level of multi talker babble was increased from an overall level of 52dB SPL to 70dB SPL.
- Rather than ramping multi talker babble on and off between trials, it is now presented continuously with a block of testing (24 trials) from either the right or left of space (see Figure 2 for multi talker babble speaker locations)

- Speaker separations increased from 15 degrees to 30 degrees for the presentation of word pairs (See Figure 2)

Listeners initially carried out a threshold task, following by practice trials and the main task, using the established individualised SNR. For the main SSiN task, participants heard two monosyllabic words within the same word group (Table I), presented sequentially from speakers separated by 30° in the presence of multi-talker babble. Participants were instructed to identify both words in order and the direction of the location shift between the first word and the second word using the touch screen tablet.

Table I — SSiN confusion word groups.

Discrimination	Word List
Complex vowel (Vc)	Pale Pool Pile Peel
Simple vowel (Vs)	Hoot Heat Heart Hurt
Initial consonant (Ci)	Chalk Talk Fork Stork
Final consonant (Cf)	Cheat Cheese Cheap Cheek

Figure 2 — *The speaker arrangement for the Spatial Speech in Noise Test.* Speakers are labelled with their azimuthal location (degrees). In the figure above, a reference speech token (“Fork”) is presented from one speaker followed by a target speech token (“Stork”) from an adjacent speaker. Testing takes place in the presence of multi-talker babble originating from either the left (blue) or right (red) speakers. Listeners are asked to face the midline throughout testing and to identify both words on the touch screen and the location shift between the words. The touch screen presented in this figure is not to scale. Speakers used for presentation of speech tokens are labelled with the speaker symbol within the speaker ring.

Statistical modeling

Each outcome variable of the SSiN (word identification and relative localisation) was tested in two parts, to include performance and reaction time. All elements of the test were analysed separately, with statistical models constructed for word identification and relative localisation performance and also for reaction time measures. Performance was captured as correct or incorrect and evaluated using logistic regression modelling. Response time was evaluated as the natural logarithm of response time in seconds, using linear regression. For word identification selections, response times above 14 s or below 100 ms were systematically removed as outliers. For relative localisation selections, reaction times below the minimum reaction time to word 2

(1.8 s), and those above 14 s, were systematically removed. Both were tested using generalized linear mixed modelling package *lme4* v1.1-26 in R version 3.6.2.

Word identification performance was tested in association with fixed effects of hearing aid condition (OSN vs. OMNI), speaker location, the azimuthal distance between word and noise (degrees), word group, word number (word 1 or word 2 in a trial), and trial number. Additionally, the following interactions were included: hearing aid condition and trial number, hearing aid condition and word number. Random baseline differences between subjects were modelled for each of accuracy and response time. The word identification reaction time model included hearing aid condition, speaker location, word-noise separation (degrees), word group, word number and trial total. An interaction between hearing aid condition and trial total and hearing aid condition and word number were also included.

Relative localisation measures (accuracy and response time) were tested in association with fixed effects of hearing aid condition, mean speaker location (degrees), word group and trial number. Interactions were included between hearing aid condition and trial total. Random baseline differences between subjects were modelled for each of accuracy and response time. Multicollinearity was deemed negligible given low variance inflation factor (VIF) for all predictors. Normality of residuals in reaction time models was ensured using QQ plots. Model performance was evaluated by calculating the area under the curve (AUC) of ROC curves for accuracy models, and goodness-of-fit (R^2) for response time models. Between-condition effect sizes were calculated using Cohen's d from the model estimate of group differences.

Hearing aid technical measurements

A GRAS 45BB KEMAR Head & Torso simulator fitted with pinna simulators, ear canal extensions, and IEC 60318-4 Ear Simulators, closely mimics the acoustic properties of the human ear. The KEMAR meets the international standards as specified by IEC: 60318-7 and ANSI: S3.36, S3.25. Pre-amplification for KEMAR's CCP microphones was provided by a Listen Sound connect 2. This was interfaced to a PC running MATLAB via an RME BabyFace Pro FS audio interface, which in turn was digitally interfaced to a MOTU 24Ao audio interface. This arrangement enables the synchronous playback and recording of multichannel stimulus and binaural response essential to correct operation of the SNR measurement technique employed.

The design of the experimental paradigm has been adapted from the behavioural SSiN. Three input SNRs were used during the technical measurements: -10dB, +5dB and +15dB. Recordings of the speech and noise signals were made in the unaided condition as well as three different hearing aid conditions, using the OPN S hearing aids coupled to occluded meatal tip ear moulds. The three hearing aid conditions were 1) full directional microphone without noise reduction, 2) omnidirectional microphone without noise reduction, 3) open sound navigator with noise reduction and 4) open sound navigator without noise reduction.

A modified version of Hagerman and Oloffson (2004) phase inversion method was used to calculate hearing aid output SNR (Hagerman & Olofsson, 2004). Speech intelligibility index (SII) weighting was applied to the output SNR measurements to reflect how different frequency regions contribute to speech understanding (Santurette et al., 2021; Wu & Stangl, 2013). SII-weighted output SNRs were calculated from output signals of KEMAR without hearing aids (unaided) and for each hearing aid condition. The separated signal and noise were each filtered into 1/3 octave bands and the SNR calculated for each band, The full bandwidth SNR was then calculated as the sum of the band SNRs after weighting each as per ANSI/ASA S3.5 (1997) classifications (American National Standards Institute, 1997).

Focus Group

To allow participants to discuss the SSiN freely, an online focus group was carried out. The focus group was guided by predetermined topic guide with open ended questions, e.g., "Describe your

experience completing the SSiN?” and follow up probing questions including those that asked about the test set up and design, comparison of this task to those carried out in usual audiology care and whether participants had any suggestions for the further development of the SSiN.

For both the open questions of the questionnaire and the online focus group, iterative-inductive thematic analysis was used to identify, analyse and report patterns (themes) within data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The present thematic analysis uses a descriptive approach with a focus on lived experience. The coded data were organised into general themes regarding the experience of carrying out the SSiN that arose from the focus group. NVivo qualitative research software (Version 12) was used for data handling, organisation, and coding. Direct quotes are included as representations of key themes and are accompanied by participant demographics to provide experiential context. The first author was the facilitator of the focus group. Coding of transcripts was carried out by the first author and themes were discussed with the other authors.

Results

All six participants completed the SSiN test twice, once with hearing aids set to OMNI and once in the OSN condition. They also completed a focus group to discuss the experience and the test design. The sample consisted of six experienced hearing aid users, each wearing bilateral Oticon OPN S receiver in the canal hearing aids with occluded soft domes. After an acclimatisation period of 4-6 weeks, each participant was invited to two separate testing sessions. Each participant completed the SSiN in the hearing aid OSN condition, and in the omnidirectional condition, as defined in the methods. The order of testing was randomised between participants. Neither the participant, nor the main experimenter knew the condition being tested during the session.

SSiN Word identification performance

Word identification performance (% correct) across azimuthal location (degrees) for OSN and OMNI conditions are shown in Figure 3. To investigate predictors of word identification performance, a generalised linear mixed effects model was conducted (AUC = 0.742, sensitivity = 0.709, specificity = 0.658) and significant predictors are outlined in Table II. Overall, there was no significant difference in word identification performance between OSN and OMNI conditions (Table II). Post hoc testing of specific speaker locations is shown in Table III.

Table II — Predictors of word identification performance. Asterisks denote significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

	X2	DF	p
Group (OSN vs OMNI)	2.589	1	0.108
Speaker location	50.651	6	<0.001 *
Speech-Noise separation	81.513	1	<0.001 *
Word Group	205.712	3	<0.001 *
Word Number (first/second)	4.370	1	0.037 *
Trial Number	0.021	1	0.883
Group x Trial Number	7.250	1	0.007 *
Group x Word Number	0.009	1	0.923

Figure 3 — Word identification (% correct) and relative localisation performance (% correct) for OSN and OMNI conditions. A) Word identification performance (%) across speaker location (degrees) in the OSN and OMNI condition, B) relative localisation performance (%) across mean speaker location (degrees) for both conditions. Error bars indicate standard error. Relative localisation chance performance = 50%.

Table III — Predictors of word identification performance. Estimate strength and significance of effects for each significant term are presented.

Term	Group	Reference	Estimate	St Error	Z	p	OR	95% CI
Group	OSN	OMNI	-0.309	0.192	-1.60	0.108	0.734	0.50 – 1.07
Speaker location	90° Left	Midline	-0.931	0.192	-4.84	<0.001*	0.394	0.27 – 0.57
	60° Left	Midline	-0.253	0.164	-1.54	0.711	0.776	0.56 – 1.07
	30° Left	Midline	-0.140	0.1479	-0.93	0.965	0.869	0.65 – 1.17
	30° Right	Midline	0.146	0.155	0.94	0.964	1.158	0.85 – 1.57
	60° Right	Midline	-0.327	0.162	-2.01	0.400	0.721	0.52 – 0.99
	90° Right	Midline	-0.814	0.197	-4.14	<0.001*	0.443	0.30 – 0.65
Word group	Vs	Vc	-0.424	0.153	-2.76	0.028*	0.655	0.48 – 0.88
	Ci	Vc	-0.855	0.145	-5.90	<0.001*	0.425	0.32 – 0.57
	Cf	Vc	-1.666	0.136	-12.27	<0.001*	0.189	0.15 – 0.25
Word number	2	1	-0.252	0.120	-2.09	0.037*	0.778	0.61 – 0.98

SSiN Word identification reaction time

Word identification reaction time, in the OMNI and OSN conditions, is presented across azimuthal location (degrees) in Figure 4. Word identification reaction time was modelled to investigate predictors, including the effect of hearing aid condition ($R^2 = 0.603$). Word identification reaction times were significantly faster in the OSN condition, compared to the OMNI condition, with an effect size of $d = 0.238$.

Figure 4 — Reaction time for word 1 and word 2 correct responses in the OMNI and OSN conditions.

Table IV — Predictors of word identification reaction time. Asterisks denote significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

	χ^2	DF	p	
Group (OSN vs OMNI)	6.148	1	0.013	*
Speaker location	80.812	6	<0.001	*
Word-noise separation	43.632	1	<0.001	*
Word Group	91.526	3	<0.001	*
Trial Number	5.548	1	0.018	*
Trial Number \times Group	7.475	1	0.006	*

Table V — Predictors of word identification reaction time.

Term	Group	Reference	Estimate	St Error	Z	p
Group	OSN	OMNI	-0.028	0.011	-2.480	0.013*
Word number	2	1	0.280	0.006	50.357	<0.001*
Location	90° Left	Midline	0.090	0.013	6.852	<0.001*
	60° Left	Midline	0.053	0.001	5.053	<0.001*
	30° Left	Midline	0.007	0.009	0.778	0.989
	30° Right	Midline	0.001	0.009	0.006	1.000
	60° Right	Midline	0.028	0.010	2.641	0.110
	90° Right	Midline	0.036	0.013	2.719	0.090
Word group	Vs	Vc	0.017	0.008	2.215	0.119
	Ci	Vc	0.013	0.008	1.643	0.354

SSiN Relative localisation performance

In addition to investigating predictors of word identification performance and reaction time, we modelled relative localisation performance (AUC = 0.771, sensitivity = 0.577, specificity = 0.874).

Here, relative localisation performance was significantly poorer in the OSN condition compared to the OMNI condition (Figure 5). There was significant main effect of speaker location, where performance was poorer at the peripheral locations compared to the midline, this pattern was present for both conditions. Lastly, accuracy significantly improved with trial number, in both conditions. Significant predictors are outlined in Table VI, with post hoc testing of specific speaker locations shown in Table VII.

Figure 5 — Predicted relative localisation performance in the OMNI and OSN hearing aid conditions. Plotted against mean speaker location (degrees). Error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals.

Table VI — Predictors of relative localisation performance.

	χ^2	DF	p
Group (OSN vs OMNI)	4.234	1	0.040
Mean speaker location	184.396	6	<0.001
Word Group	2.326	3	0.507
Trial Number	4.091	1	0.043
Group x Trial Number	0.535	1	0.465

SSiN Relative localisation reaction time

Relative localisation reaction time was modelled with moderate fit ($R^2 = 0.315$). This reaction time measure was the time taken for participants to respond with the location shift between reference and target words (either left or right). Response times were significantly faster for the OSN condition relative to the OMNI condition (mean difference = 39 ms, SE = 7 ms), with an effect size of $d = 0.207$ (see Figure 6).

Table VII — Predictors of relative localisation performance. Estimate strength and significance of effects for each significant term are presented.

Term	Group	Reference	Estimate	St Error	Z	p	OR	95% CI
Group	OSN	OMNI	-0.398	0.193	-2.058	0.040	0.672	0.46 – 0.98
Mean speaker location	75° Left	Midline	-1.797	0.199	-9.037	<0.001	0.166	0.11 – 0.25
	45° Left	Midline	-0.808	0.209	-3.864	0.002	0.446	0.29 – 0.67
	15° Left	Midline	-0.125	0.226	-0.551	0.998	0.883	0.57 – 1.38
	15° Right	Midline	-0.471	0.216	-2.182	0.302	0.625	0.41 – 0.95
	45° Right	Midline	-0.906	0.207	-4.372	<0.001	0.404	0.27 – 0.61
	75° Right	Midline	-1.817	0.199	-9.133	<0.001	0.162	0.11 – 0.24

Figure 6 — Log reaction time for relative localisation selections in the OMNI and OSN conditions. Results plotted as a function of mean speaker locations (degrees). Significant predictors are outlined in Table VIII, with post hoc testing of specific speaker locations shown in Table IX. There was no significant interaction between hearing aid condition and mean speaker location. Furthermore, despite the main effect of condition, post hoc testing did not show significant differences between conditions at any individual speakers. Lastly, responses became significantly slower with trial number.

Table VIII — Predictors of relative localisation reaction time.

	χ^2	DF	p
Group (OSN vs OMNI)	6.390	1	0.011
Mean speaker location	20.611	6	0.002
Word Group	30.241	3	<0.001
Trial Number	38.044	1	<0.001
Trial Number × Group	0.170	1	0.680
Mean speaker location x Group	7.259	6	0.298

Table IX — Estimate strength and significance of effects for each significant term are presented.

Term	Group	Reference	Estimate	St Error	Z	p
Group	OSN	OMNI	-0.052	0.024	-2.207	0.011
Location	75° Left	Midline	0.064	0.020	3.272	0.019
	45° Left	Midline	0.024	0.020	1.243	0.877
	15° Left	Midline	-0.009	0.020	-0.448	0.999
	15° Right	Midline	0.019	0.020	0.944	0.965
	45° Right	Midline	0.011	0.020	0.556	0.998
	75° Right	Midline	0.007	0.020	0.361	1.000
Word group	Vs	Vc	0.019	0.011	1.790	0.278
	Ci	Vc	0.011	0.011	1.066	0.710
	Cf	Vc	0.053	0.011	4.999	<0.001

Hearing aid technical measurements

Technical measurements were completed to investigate how the hearing aids respond to the SSiN experimental design used in the behavioural study (Figure 7 and 8).

Figure 7 — SII weighted output SNR from hearing aid conditions (OMNI and OSN) and the unaided condition with multi-talker babble presented in front of KEMAR. During testing, multi-talker babble was presented from the frontal speaker locations. Results are plotted as a function of speaker location (degrees). A, B and C of this figure are results from an input SNR of +5 dB; D, E and F presented results from an input SNR of -10 dB.

Figure 8 — SII weighted output SNR from hearing aid conditions (OMNI and OSN) and the unaided condition with multi-talker babble presented from behind KEMAR. Data are plotted as a function of speaker location and for two input SNRs (+5 dB and -10 dB). Multi-talker babble is presented from behind the KEMAR.

Participants described the process of carrying out the SSiN and compared the task to those they have experienced within the audiology service provision pathway. Three key themes were identified: 1) speech as a meaningful stimulus, 2) difficulty levels and 3) equipment and test set up. Table X summarises actionable changes that could improve the SSiN user experience, based on the findings of this work.

Speech as a meaningful stimulus

Participants reported the specific benefits of the SSiN test compared to the traditional audiology tests they were accustomed to (as noted above, routine audiology clinics often do not use speech

tests in the UK). Particularly the use of speech tokens and background noise in the SSiN was found to be beneficial compared to the regular use of pure tone testing in audiology.

I certainly found it useful because the test concentrated on a speech element and not on tones and beeps, which to me is doesn't relate in the real world, because I can't hear those things. Anyway, my biggest issue has always been speech. (EF, 49 years old)

I think it was just so different to any audiology test setup before, related to speech which is my main problem in day-to-day life. (KL, 70 years old)

If that was some way that modern hearing centres could incorporate tests like that, because most of the time it is about speed. It's about hearing people so that we can communicate, and people don't talk and clicks and beeps and tones. (EF, 49 years old)

The tests were a little bit more realistic, because you had the background noise, you have to get the direction, you have to actually distinguish the words, which is something that I struggled with. (EF, 49 years old)

Difficulty levels

The dual nature of the task, particular the inclusion of a measure of relative localisation, added a level of difficulty and challenged the listener. Participants commented that this made the task more comparable to day-to-day challenges of listening in noise.

Oh, I wish this could happen more often. Because I feel as though this is really testing me. And I'm really beginning to understand what goes on with my hearing in difficult situations. (LM, 74 years old)

I think I could hear, but the main challenge was distinguishing where the second word was coming from. I thought I found that quite challenging, but challenging is actually good. (KL, 70 years old)

However, focus group participants also mentioned that although the SSiN testing experience was positively challenging, they did feel fatigued due to the duration and concentration required. Also, due to the difficulty of the task, participants reported their discomfort in having to guess some of the answers.

I thought the whole thing was very positive, it was quite draining. It's tiring. (KL, 70 years old)

It was a slight worry at the time because I felt I was guessing some of the time. So, I suppose it sort of bothered me, it bothered me that I might be getting the results wrong. (AB, 81 years old)

Equipment and test set up

Comments were made about the physical testing space and equipment used within the SSiN. Some also reported that the repetition in the task meant that words became familiar as the test went on and this familiarity sped up their responses. Others commented that the words were difficult to tell apart and therefore appropriate for the task.

Quite an experience being in that anechoic room aiming for the chair as I walked in. I'm not quite sure where my feet would go, because I was a bit nervous in there to start with. (AB, 81 years old)

With usage, the words became reasonably familiar (which speeded up the response). Some words had a characteristic element (e.g., sibilance) which made them easier to distinguish. The words were all familiar, but

without the graphics I would have really struggled (i.e., would have had difficulty in many cases in—say—repeating them). (AB, 81 years old)

I did find I was pressing quite hard and so changed from using my index finger to my thumb and then changed the way I was holding the screen too. (LM, 74 years old)

Table X — Summary of qualitative feedback and SSiN design implications.

Area of evaluation	Summary of feedback	Actionable changes
Hardware	Touchscreen difficult to use	Touch screen to be updated
Human factors	The test is quite tiring, and breaks are needed to avoid fatigue	Regular breaks should be encouraged and emphasized before testing
Test environment	Anechoic chamber comfortable overall but needs some getting used to	Include a period of time to adjust to anechoic chamber before testing.
Stimuli	Low number of words, background noise only from the front.	Background noise from the rear should be introduced. Consider additional word groups
Test instructions	Main difficulty was understanding the relative localisation task	Clear instructions or demo video to emphasis the spatial elements of the relative localisation task

Discussion

The aims of this study were to consider how the SSiN could be used to assess advanced hearing aid features and to present listeners' perspectives and experiences of completing the task. After fitting all participants with the same hearing aid type, SSiN results were compared between two directionality settings: omnidirectional (OMNI) and adaptive directionality (OSN). At the group level, OSN did not improve word identification, was detrimental to relative localisation performance, but reduced reaction times, compared to the OMNI setting. Hearing aid output measurements showed that OSN to improved output SNR across azimuth compared to the unaided and OMNI conditions. The introduction of a rear noise source and less favourable input SNRs, compared to those used in the behavioural SSiN, resulted in the largest differences between OSN and OMNI conditions. From the participants' perspective, the SSiN demonstrates an assessment scenario that better reflects real world listening, compared to current audiological assessment methods.

The present study trialled the applicability of the SSiN in the assessment of Oticon's adaptive directionality (OSN) and comparison to omnidirectionality. Such assessment methods could have potential to assist audiologists' clinical decision making regarding the patient candidacy for these hearing aid features as well as the identification of patient factors that might influence hearing aid uptake or benefit including listening effort, relative localisation performance, and speech in noise perception abilities. In the present study, the SSiN was used to compare word identification and relative localisation performance and associated reaction times between OSN and OMNI hearing aid settings. Overall, there were no significant differences in word identification performance between OSN and OMNI settings. This is consistent with previous literature that also found no significant difference between these settings, when the background noise was speech and OSN did not significantly reduce word identification performance compared to OMNI, at any speaker location (Browning et al., 2019). The double blinded nature of this study is a strength of the present study as the lack of blinding and randomisation has been noted as a methodological limitation of previous studies involving the behavioural assessment of hearing aid algorithms (Lakshmi et al., 2021). The hearing aid acclimatisation period (4–6 weeks) is another strength to this study, which other hearing aid studies of OSN have not been able to implement (Browning et al., 2019). The small sample size ($n = 6$) is a limitation. However, this study forms the ideal starting

point for planning a larger trial using the SSiN as an outcome measure of auditory rehabilitation tools or hearing aid features. A larger trial was planned but postponed due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Results from power analysis suggest that the present study was significant underpowered, and more participants ($n = 21$) are needed to determine whether the performance differences observed are accurate. It is possible that the small OMNI vs OSN effects observed are present but cannot be confirmed due to the study being underpowered, rather than concluding that no effects are present. Future behavioural SSiN trials could include the addition of a rear noise source and use of a range of SNRs to explore how advanced hearing aid features impact performance within dynamic, realistic listening situations.

After the behavioural study, the SSiN was reviewed by participants during an online focus group to gain feedback about the usability, accessibility, and overall experience of carrying out the SSiN. The review also included how the SSiN test paradigm relates to both the challenging natural everyday listening environments, and to common audiology tests currently used in the clinic. Qualitative research has been used alongside clinical intervention development to optimise intervention content, delivery, and acceptability (Donovan et al., 2002; Moore et al., 2015; Vickers et al., 2021) and actively involving patients and the public in research can lead to better, clearer, more relevant research (National Institute for Health Research, 2021). In healthcare research, qualitative methods such as telephone interviews, semi-structured interviews, surveys and focus groups have been used to evaluate health promotion activities (Burn et al., 2021), develop health education resources (Ferguson et al., 2018) and health intervention strategies (Vincent et al., 2006). In fact, a lack of stakeholder/patient involvement has been reported to be a key weakness in the development of health education tools (Van Velsen et al., 2013) as this could result in the creation of tools and resources that are not aligned with the target audience/end user's needs (Ferguson et al., 2018). Within hearing research, patient involvement has been found to be particularly beneficial during the design of communication tools, as end users were put at the centre of the process (Ellis & Kurniawan, 2000; Hanssen & Dahl, 2016). This process can also help identify unforeseen positive contributions or limitations of the product. In the present study, participants reported positive experiences of carrying out the SSiN as it was a challenging task of localisation and speech identification in the presence of background noise. In general, participants liked the experience of speech testing, which is not often conducted in routine audiology clinics in the UK (Parmar et al., 2021). They also felt the task was challenging but that it was a better representation of everyday listening experiences with multiple noise sources and moving target words. Currently, in the UK the guidance for adult hearing assessment (NICE: NG98) does not recommend using speech testing (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2018). Our participants gave a different perspective and pointed out the value of undergoing ecologically valid testing. Participants also reflected on specific difficulties and challenges they had whilst completing the SSiN. Key areas of evaluation are presented in this study, alongside some actionable changes that could take place to improve usability and accessibility during testing. These areas should be considered before the task is used more regularly within research or clinical practice.

Conclusion

There is potential for the Spatial Speech in Noise test to be used in the assessment of advanced hearing aid features, like adaptive directionality algorithms. In this small dataset, the SSiN detected participants' reaction times were reduced in the adaptive directionality condition compared to omnidirectionality, despite word identification performance remaining constant between conditions. The SSiN could help clinicians assess a listeners' candidacy for these features and assess hearing aid benefit. The task should be further developed to address user feedback and enhance ecological validity.

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Comments

Comments from Sarah Knight:

Thanks for the opportunity to read this work! I have a few comments, as follows:

In general, I felt as though the manuscript could do with some reorganisation and streamlining to make it clearer for the reader. For example: i) there's repetition of information within the Participants section; ii) it might be useful to explain the OSN system before the HA fitting rather than afterwards; iii) the different statistical models are very similar to each other, so it might be clearer to list the included effects in a table instead of using prose; iv) the justification for including a focus group might have been more useful in the Introduction rather than the Discussion. There are also a few typos here and there!

Could the SSiN be described in a little more detail? I appreciate that the task is taken from Bizley et al. (2015), but it would be useful to include enough information for the current paper to function as a standalone manuscript. In particular, could the authors specify the number of talkers in the multi-talker babble, the gender(s) of targets vs. babble talkers, the nature of the adaptive procedure, and the duration of the gap between word 1 and word 2?

Just curious: is there a reason why 14s was chosen as the upper cut-off for the RTs?

The blue colour in Figure 2 hasn't reproduced very well!

What was the rationale for the choice of SNRs used in the HA technical measurements, and how did those SNRs relate to the SNRs presented to the 6 participants?

Figure 8 indicates the use of a rear noise source for the technical measurements – something which is mentioned again during the Discussion section – but this choice isn't mentioned or justified in the Methods section, nor is it explicitly discussed in the Results. Could the authors explain more about this methodological decision?

In general, the outcome of the technical measurements is presented with very little explanation in the Results/Discussion sections. Would it be possible to summarise these data and give some indication of how they relate to the behavioural results?

The Group x Trial interaction (Table II) seems likely to be an important one, reflecting fatigue or listening effort, but it isn't broken down or discussed. Could the authors go into more detail on this point?

I'm not sure what Figure 5 is showing and how this relates to the lower panel (B) of Figure 3.

If I've understood correctly, then the authors didn't test for an interaction between Group (hearing aid condition) and mean speaker location when examining the relative localisation performance. Given the nature of the task (i.e. localisation), and the apparent differences in panel B of Figure 3, I'd be curious to know if this interaction was significant and – if so – how the authors would interpret this result.

I appreciate that these are preliminary data, but the finding that OSN reduces RTs but impairs relative localisation seems to merit further discussion and interpretation. Why might such a finding arise?

Comments from Leslie Bernstein:

The focus of the paper, as indicated by its title and content, is on evaluating the benefits of employing within hearing aids, directional microphones and associated algorithms. The paper recognizes that the most common ways to enhance speech intelligibility in noise are to employ noise suppression and directional microphones. The two primary conditions compared, however, were one in which omnidirectional microphones were coupled with no noise suppression (OMNI) and one in which directional microphones were coupled with noise suppression (OSN). This apparent confound makes it difficult to assess which of the effects reported stemmed from the use of directional microphones, the implementation of noise suppression, or some combination of the two. The Discussion characterizes the experiment as having compared results “between two directionality settings.” The fact that noise reduction was employed in only one of those settings (OMNI) is lost completely. It would have been most revealing had the psychophysical measures been obtained with the same combination of processing as was used to make the technical measures. Those were a two-by-two arrangement of the activation of directionality and noise reduction.

It would be helpful to comment on the potential effects of fitting hearing-aid users with varying degrees of experience with new devices. Was any account taken of the similarities or dissimilarities between the aids and algorithms to which they were accustomed and those of the fitted Oticon devices?

It would seem of benefit for the authors to comment on the post-hoc tests, the results of which are listed in Table III.

While word identification and relative localization reaction times were found to be significantly shorter in the OSN condition, consideration of the variances accounted for and small effect sizes leads to the question of whether those significant differences are meaningful in a practical sense.

It is worth noting that the progressively poorer relative localization performance found as azimuthal angle was increased is consistent with decades of literature concerning binaural performance.

Any discussion of the results of the technical measures obtained and reported on pages 10 and 11 is conspicuously absent.

Especially given that a closed set of speech was employed, it would seem of benefit to compare performance in both the SSiN and relative localization measures on the first vs. second half of testing and not only by trial number.

The recognized and substantial scientific benefits of using speech notwithstanding, I found the comments of the focus group concerning the “meaningfulness” of the stimuli vis a vis those typically employed in clinics to be quite as expected and of little practical value. It is no surprise that laypersons would find speech stimuli to be more “useful,” “more realistic,” and more desirable. Laypersons cannot be expected to, and usually do not, understand the diagnostic value of specialized stimuli designed to measure specific aspects of auditory processing. After all, most of what has been learned about specific aspects of auditory processing via behavioral experiments has capitalized on the use of novel stimuli that were far from being “ecologically valid.”

The results of the study were such that the use of the OSN condition provided no benefit in terms of word recognition while simultaneously degrading relative localization performance. Had there been some positive tradeoff, e.g., superior word identification in the face of degraded relative localization performance or superior relative localization performance in the face of degraded word identification, then OSN might be considered to be of some benefit. Neither of those outcomes occurred. With regard to the OSN yielding significantly shorter reaction times, the magnitude of the effect appears to be quite small, at best.

Considering the results, I'm a bit puzzled as to why the authors view this study as "the ideal starting point" for a larger trial.

Comments from Enrico varano:

This paper is a preliminary report on the suitability of the Spatial Speech in Noise Test (SSiN) as a tool for (clinical) testing of advanced hearing aid features such as adaptive directionality algorithms. As stated by the authors, this n=6 study is a good pilot for a larger study. In my opinion, if the results presented in this study can be replicated and expanded upon in a larger study with adequate statistical power, this will constitute a significant and clinically applicable contribution to the field.

A couple suggestions below.

Methodological (for the larger study):

I would focus on removing training (lines 340-1) and tiring effects (lines 277-8 and 333-4) with more careful experimental design and practical/operational care. For example, longer breaks, shorter and more numerous sessions and clearer explanation of tasks may be beneficial.

I found the combination of closed-form testing and open participant feedback of value. These preliminary results suggest that listening effort (incl. the parasitic tiring and learning) is the main driver of the effects seen. Performing a battery of cognitive tests on the participants would be a great way to understand the mechanisms underlying the results shown.

Formatting/Clarity:

A careful review and re-organisation of the methods section may benefit the clarity. For example, a re-introduction to SSiN and Oticon's OSN would be helpful (the paragraph following the heading on line 101 would best fit near lines 75-78). Importantly, it is also not clear what kind of processing takes place under the two conditions compared.

line 113: I'd specify that 'speakers' refers to loud speakers, not individual talkers

Figure 1 is hardly legible

Figure 2: blue is hard to see against black

lines 150-158 would benefit of a table or figure summary

lines 174-176 need clarification

lines 209-214 contain repetitions

figures 3, 4 and 6: I'd make the plots more comparable by plotting conditions on the same axes or showing thicker axes grids

tables 6-9 lack the * to highlight statistically significant p values (present in tables 2-5)

Typos/grammar/style:

line 67-68: repetition of 'bilateral'

line 42: microphone -> microphones

line 123: following -> followed

line 171: awkward phrasing imho

line 182: missing capitalisation

figure 6 caption: inconsistent font

line 295: formatting

Comments from Deniz Başkent:

I did not have the chance to read the paper yet but saw the talk, which was great! So much work is done already!

I tried to ask this question after the talk, but there was little time and wanted to elaborate some more here: The microphones are located at different places for different HAs and this alone can have an effect on both lateralisation and externalisation of sounds. It would be great if there is a chance to look at users with different HAs with different microphone locations.

Also, reaction time comparisons across NH and HA user participants may be difficult as HA users tend to be older. If reaction time is measured by onset of response or finger tap, either measure can be affected by aging.

Up-to-date comments can be found on [PubPeer](#).